

Variation in the Amounts of Ammoniacal and Nitric Nitrogen in Rain Water of Different Countries and the Origin of Nitric Nitrogen in the Atmosphere

BY N. R. DHAR AND ATMA RAM.

It is well known that an appreciable quantity of nitrites and nitrates falls on the earth's surface with rain water. The following table indicates a few observations.

Place.	Wt. of nitric N per acre brought down by the annual rainfall.
Caracas, Venezuela ...	7.87 lb.
St. Denis, Island of Re-union ...	9.437
Lieb Frauenberg, Alsace ...	0.5214
Rothamsted, England ...	1.33

The nitrites and nitrates present in rain water are derived from the nitric nitrogen occurring in the atmosphere. The nitric nitrogen present in the atmosphere exists either as the oxides of nitrogen or as ammonium nitrate and nitrite. These are washed down to the soil by the rain and form an important source of nitrogenous compounds for the nutrition of plants. What is the origin of this nitric nitrogen? It was believed that the oxides of nitrogen owe their origin to thunder storms in the upper air; nitrogen and oxygen combine to form oxides of nitrogen due to electric discharge. But thunder storms do not occur frequently. If the presence of the oxides of nitrogen is to be ascribed to thunder storms, they will be washed down to the earth by the rain which follows thunder storms and no oxides of nitrogen should be present in the atmosphere on ordinary days. But this is not the case. The amount of the oxides of nitrogen present in air on ordinary days is practically the same as that present on days when thunder storm occurs. There is no relation between the variation of the nitrite and nitrate content of the atmosphere and the incidence of thunder storms.

According to Moore (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1555), sunlight causes a slight union of nitrogen and oxygen in the air, resulting in the formation of oxides of nitrogen. Dhar and Sanyal (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 926) have observed the formation of traces of nitrite when air freed from impurities is bubbled through conductivity water in presence of mercury vapour lamp light and in sunlight.

The photochemical combination of nitrogen and oxygen appears to contribute a small part of the total nitric nitrogen present in the atmosphere. Very recently Gopal Rao and Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, 199, 422) have advanced the view that the important source of nitrites and nitrates in the atmosphere, is the photo-oxidation of ammonia by air in presence of sunlight.

It is well known that ammonia occurs in the atmosphere to an appreciable extent. The ammonia is derived from the decomposition of nitrogenous organic matter, from the burning of coal, etc. The air of manufacturing towns appears to be more rich in ammonia than the air of rural districts; for the huge consumption of coal in industrial centres sets free large amounts of ammonia. Thus Smith found in England 0.97 mg. of ammonia per litre of rain in the country (2.502 lbs. per acre) and 5.14 mg. in the town (13.4 lbs. per acre); and in Scotland 0.53 mg. in the country (1.381 lb. per acre) and 3.81 mg. in towns (9.928 lbs. per acre). J. A. Barral estimated that Paris received annually 20.83 lbs. of ammonia per acre and A. Bineau showed that Lyons had 73.53 lbs. per acre. This ammonia is continuously undergoing oxidation to nitrite and nitrate by the oxygen of the air under the influence of ultraviolet rays from the sun.

From the theory of nitrification advanced from these laboratories, it is expected that the ratio of nitric to ammoniacal nitrogen in the rain water, available in tropical countries should be much greater than the ratio obtained in the rain water collected in temperate and cold climates. In order to test this point, we have undertaken a systematic analysis of rain water, as no satisfactory data on this question are available. The procedure adopted in the analysis of rain water was as follows:

The rain water was collected in large porcelain dishes placed on a tall stool in an open space. A definite volume of the freshly collected rain water, usually 300 c.c., was taken in a distilling flask and evaporated to 20 c.c. in presence of potassium hydroxide, so that the ammonia present in rain water in the free and

combined states was removed. The nitrite and nitrate of rain water now present as potassium salts were reduced by Devarda's alloy. The ammonia obtained by the reduction was caught in two small flasks containing dilute sulphuric acid. After complete reduction of the nitrates and nitrites, the contents of the two flasks were made up to 250 c.c. The amount of ammonia so obtained was estimated by the colorimetric method using the Duboscq type of colorimeter and Nessler's reagent. The amount of nitrogen present in the ammonia obtained by reduction represents the sum of the nitric and nitrous nitrogen present in rain water. From this, the nitrogen due to the nitrites was deducted. The nitrites were estimated separately by the colorimetric method applying the well known α -naphthylamine sulphanic acid test. The amount of ammonia present in rain water in the free and combined states can be easily found by the colorimetric method taking the original rain water and comparing it with a standard ammonium chloride solution. That the ammonia obtained by the reduction was not due to impurities present in the Devarda's alloy and the alkali, a blank experiment, using the same amount of alloy and alkali as used in the analysis of rain water was always performed with conductivity water, and the amount of ammonia so obtained, if at all, was always deducted from the actual amounts available after the reduction. In the blank experiment with conductivity water, the alloy and alkali were heated in a flask in two instalments for a total period of 8 hours in order to obtain comparable results. In order that all the nitrite and nitrate present in rain water be reduced, the reduction should be carried on at least twice and the total time required for the reduction was 8 hours. It is well known that the estimation of small amounts of nitrates present in a large volume of water is difficult because it is exceedingly tedious to reduce the nitrates completely on prolonged boiling with alkali and Devarda's alloy. In our experiments, we boiled the rain water after concentration with alkali and the alloy in a flask in two instalments for a total period of 8 hours, each time adding a fresh sample of the alkali and the alloy. We have observed that most of the samples of Devarda's alloy contain small amounts of ammonium compounds, nitrites and nitrates. Hence in all our experiments, the amounts of ammonia derived from the impurities in alloy were always taken into account. In this connection, the following observations of Thresh ("The examination of waters and water supplies." 1913, p.

295) will be of interest:—“In no other determination do results differ so widely. On more than one occasion, I have had to give an opinion upon water which had been submitted to various well known analysts. The other determinations recorded in the analyses have usually been concordant, but the nitric nitrogen had varied enormously. This has not been due to any change in the water, as in some cases the samples were taken at the same time. The difference appears to be due to the methods employed.”

We are of the opinion, therefore, that the estimation of small quantities of nitrate present in rain water is likely to be vitiated if special precautions are not taken and it seems likely that the earlier results on the nitric nitrogen content of rain water obtained by some previous workers may not be quite correct.

The following are the experimental results:

Date.	Ammoniacal N mg./litre.	Nitric N mg./litre.	Ratio of nitric to ammoniacal N.
Aug. 21, 1932	0.20	0.50	2.5
Sept. 2, 1932	1.02	2.56	2.5
„ 3, „	0.17	0.70	4.1
„ 3, „	0.16	0.70	4.4
„ 4, „	0.24	0.70	3.1
„ 5, „	0.17	0.61	3.6
„ 6, „	0.11	0.45	4.1
„ 6, „	0.10	0.43	4.3
„ 16, „	0.60	1.65	2.7
„ 16, „	0.28	0.88	3.1
„ 16, „	0.24	0.87	3.6
Oct. 23, „	0.37	0.81	2.2
„ 23, „	0.36	0.86	2.4
Mean	0.31	0.90	3.3

The foregoing results show that in all cases, the ratio of nitric to ammoniacal nitrogen is much greater than unity and the average is 3.3. It will be interesting to note that the ratio of the nitric nitrogen

to ammoniacal nitrogen in rain water collected after the end of a heavy shower is greater than in the water collected in the beginning of the shower. It is difficult to explain this observation and we are carrying on experiments in order to throw light on this problem.

Our experimental results are in agreement with our theory of nitrification in the atmosphere. We have observed that the rain water collected at Allahabad is generally slightly acidic probably due to the presence of free nitric and nitrous acids.

It will be interesting to compare our values with those obtained in colder countries. According to Lawes and Gilbert the average amount of total nitrogen in country rain water is about 0·7 parts in million parts of water, whilst our value is 1·21 in the same volume of rain water.

We are of opinion that in tropical countries, the ratio of nitric to ammoniacal nitrogen is higher than unity due to two reasons, (1) the increased photo-oxidation of ammonia and its compounds to nitrous and nitric acids under the action of sunlight; (2) the slow combination of nitrogen and oxygen forming oxides of nitrogen in presence of the ultra violet light of the sun.

In the following tables we have collected the amounts of ammoniacal, nitric and total nitrogen available in rain water at different places.

TABLE I.

Non-industrial Places (Tropics).

Place.	Latitude.	Ammoniacal N in lbs. per acre.	Nitric N in lbs. per acre.	Ratio $\frac{\text{nitric N}}{\text{ammon. N}}$	Total amount of N brought down by rain in lbs. per acre.
British Guiana	5·0 N	1·006	2·541	2·5	3·547
Venezuela	10·30 N	—	7·870	—	—
Barbados	13·10 N	1·009	2·443	2·42	3·452
Reunion	21 S	—	9·437	—	—
Allahabad	25·28 N	2·020	5·865	2·9	7·885
Mean	—	1·384	5·631	2·6	—

TABLE II.

Non-industrial Places (Temperate.)

Place.	Latitude.	Ammonia- cal N in lbs. per acre.	Nitric N in lbs. per acre.	Ratio nitric N ammoniacal N	Total amount of N brought down in lbs. per acre.
DehraDun	30·19 N	2·037	1·368	0·67	3·405
Kokstad	30·34 S	1·702	1·021	0·6	2·723
Mississippi	33 S	—	—	—	3·636
Grahams town	33·19 S	1·443	1·16	0·804	2·603
Kansas	38 N	2·63	1·06	0·4	3·69
New Zealand coast	40 S	0·6	0·8	1·33	1·4
Cornell Mt. Vernon	40·26 N	2·64	1·755	0·66	4·395
Alsace	48·3 N	—	0·521	—	—
Rothamsted	51·49 N	2·04	1·33	0·50	3·97
Iceland	64·40 N	0·802	0·263	0·328	1·065
Hebrides	56·50 N	0·313	0·289	0·93	0·600
Ottawa	59·3 N	2·99	1·755	0·59	4·745
Mean	—	1·436	1·02	0·72	2·686

TABLE III.

Industrial Places.

Place.	Latitude.	Ammonia- cal N in lbs. per acre.	Nitric N in lbs. per acre.	Ratio nitric N ammoniacal N	Total N brought down by rain in lbs per acre.
TROPICS					
Cawnpore (India)	26·28 N	2·482	0·768	0·31	3·25
Pretoria (S. Africa)	25·25 S	6·587	1·083	0·16	7·67
Mean	—	4·534	0·925	0·235	5·46
TEMPERATE					
Cedar (S. Africa)	32·22 S	7·083	1·321	0·16	8·409
Utah (U. S. A.)	39·30 N	5·06	0·356	0·07	5·416
Paris	48·51 N	—	—	—	8·93
Gembloux (Belgium)	50·33 N	—	—	—	9·2
Gröningen	51·57 N	4·0	1·2	0·3	5·2
Mean	—	5·382	0·959	0·179	7·431

From the foregoing survey of results obtained in the analysis of rain water in different countries, it seems that the ratio of nitric to ammoniacal nitrogen is greater in tropical than in countries situated in the temperate and frigid zones.

Moreover, it appears that the total nitrogen which falls with rain water is also appreciably greater in tropical countries. This increased amount of nitrogen which is available in the rain water of tropical countries may be ascribed to the following reasons:

(i) The combination of nitrogen and oxygen present in the air in presence of ultraviolet light from the sun.

(ii) The increased ammonification of the nitrogenous compounds present in the soil due to light absorption.

In publications from these laboratories we have shown that not only nitrification in the soil but also ammonification is accelerated by sunlight. In tropical countries, the surface of the earth received more sunlight than in temperate and cold countries and naturally there should be more nitrification and ammonification. A part of the ammonia escapes into the air and this addition of ammonia to the atmosphere appears to be more prominent in tropical than in non-tropical climates, because the soils in tropical countries attain a much higher temperature than in non-tropical countries. We have carried on experiments with urea solutions mixed with soil and have observed that there is more ammonia formed from urea in sunlight than in the dark and an appreciable amount of ammonia formed from the urea escapes into the air. In this connection the following remarks of Miller (*Chem. Soc. Annual Reports*, 1913, p. 212) will be of interest: "We have evidence that the fairly heavy soil at Rothamsted loses ammonia for some weeks after the application of ammonium salts and it is possible that some soils are more or less continuously giving into the air small portions of the ammonia produced from organic residues. Some soils may be expected to lose more ammonia than is returned in the rain, whilst others may gain in this manner more than they lose." Consequently in tropical countries, the atmosphere is richer not only in nitrites and nitrates but it also contains more ammonia than in non-tropical centres free from large industries.

It is well known that in industrial areas, the atmosphere is rich in ammonia and its compounds because of the combustion of large quantities of coal and decomposition of organic matter and that is why, the amount of ammonia in places like Paris,

Gembloux (Belgium), Pretoria, Cedar (South Africa), Utah (U. S. A.), Gröningen, etc., is higher than in country districts free from big industries. It will be interesting to note also that the ammonia content of rain water collected at Cawnpore (India), which is an industrial town is greater than that of Allahabad and Dehradun, which are non-industrial places. It seems certain, however, that the ammonia content of rain water of non-industrial places in the temperate and frigid zones is appreciably less than in places situated in the tropics. Hence the total nitrogen which comes to the soil from the rain water in tropical countries is appreciably greater than in non-tropical places. Consequently, the following statements of Miller and Russel need modification: "No countenance is given to the general belief that the Indian rainfall is richer in nitrogen than that of England." "That great differences in climate do not coincide with material differences in the amounts of nitrogen brought down by the rains." (cf. Miller, *Chem. Soc. Annual Reports*, 1906, p. 269).

"It is evident from all these results that as a source of combined nitrogen, the rain is of no great importance to crops—an average of wheat or barley will contain eight times nitrogen." (cf. Miller, *Chem. Soc. Annual Reports*, 1913, p. 211).

"It is now recognised that the quantities of nitrogenous compounds present in rain water are too insignificant to exert any appreciable effect" (cf. Russel, *Chem. Soc. Annual Reports*, 1919, p. 182).

In poor tropical countries, artificial manures are not much in use and naturally the crops and plants have to depend for their nitrogen requirements upon the soil which is hardly manured artificially and thus the supply of combined nitrogen from the rain, which is more important in tropical countries than in non-tropical countries, appears to assume importance in tropical agriculture.

SUMMARY.

(1) Careful analysis of rain water at Allahabad shows that the average amount of ammoniacal nitrogen is 0.31 part in million parts of water and of nitric nitrogen is 0.9 part in the same volume of rain water.

(2) The ratio of nitric to ammoniacal nitrogen has been found to be 2.9.

(3) This high ratio is due to the increased photo-oxidation of the atmospheric ammonia and its compounds by the oxygen of the air in presence of the ultra-violet light of the sun and the photo-chemical combination of nitrogen and oxygen of the air in sunlight.

(4) From the summary of the analysis of rain water carried on in various other countries, it appears that the ratio of nitric to ammoniacal nitrogen is greater in tropical countries than in non-tropical ones.

(5) Moreover it also appears that the total nitrogen, which falls with rain water on the surface of the earth is appreciably greater in tropical countries than in non-tropical countries. This is likely to be due to the increased photochemical combination of nitrogen and oxygen in tropical sunlight and the increase of ammonification of the nitrogenous compounds present in the soil due to sunlight and the escape of ammonia produced in ammonification to the atmosphere.

(6) The amount of ammoniacal nitrogen in rain water of industrial centres can be high and seems to depend on the coal consumption and decomposition of organic matter.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
ALLAHABAD UNIVERSITY.

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